

**ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS OF THE SUSTAINABLE
NEIGHBORHOODS IN THE URBAN SETTLEMENTS - CASE STUDY:
SHABAKE 2 NEIGHBORHOOD OF SARDASHT CITY, IRAN**

Shirko Ahmadi^{1i*},

Rezgar Hamzeh pour^{2,}

Mehdi Ehsasikhah³

¹Young Researchers and Elite Club, Sardasht (Urmia) Branch,
Islamic Azad University, Sardasht (Urmia), Iran

²M.A Graduated of Geography and Urban Planning,
Tehran University, Iran

³Masters Land Preparation Planning, Tehran University, Iran

Abstract:

The neighborhood is the main base of urban body and the future of social life balance in the cities has much dependence to keep the unit of the neighborhood. It is the neighborhoods that make pleasant living in the large cities. During 20th century using the idea of residential neighborhood has been based for so many modern urban development theories and this idea has been welcomed to deal with various urban problems such as management issues, social and human relationships, health and welfare problems and also semantic and identity dimensions. Sardasht city is facing with various dilemmas regarding optimal management of spatial organization of the city. And the present approach in its major and centralized management has not led to sustainable urban development due to the lack relying on local building, public participation, and sustainable systems of local ecologic and thus meets the real needs of residents. Therefore, development of urban neighborhoods has known as the pilot point of developing sustainable management of the city. This study is focusing on this goal and testing the modern approach of sustainable neighborhood-oriented in the system of modern urban management in the Shabake 2 district. The method of the research is applied-development and the survey method is a way to doing it .statistical population of this research consists of all residents of Shabake 2 district of Sardasht which among

ⁱ Correspondence: email shirkoahmadi@gmail.com

them 320 persons selected as random sampling for statistical sample. The data has analyzed by SPSS software. Results indicate that the value of sustainability of the neighborhood in terms of residents is in the moderate level. Also, findings of research indicate that there is difference among various places of this neighborhood in terms of sustainability. According to findings of research seems that the most important implementation strategy for sustainability is applying coordinated organizing strategies and empowering the neighborhood at the national-regional and local level.

Keywords: local sustainable development, urban management, Shabake 2 district, Sardasht city

1. Introduction

Following developments in contemporary urban context and replacement of modern urban structure instead of old urban setting, role and status of urban neighborhoods is of paramount importance. It seems that changes generally in various factors of economic, social, environmental and body of the cities and especially in the districts has had significant negative impacts on their performance to meet the needs of residents. Evidence suggests that new neighborhoods build by humans faced with very different experiences after elapsing a relatively long period of time. Consequently associated issues to new developments of the city and to response them some theories has also been proposed in the past until now, for example we can refer to high-rise building, compact city, increasing the density and urban development. Studying mentioned theories, especially recent theories shows that sustainable neighborhood development has not been seriously considered yet (Azizi, 2006: 36). Sustainability is a concept that its main focus on maintaining assets (human, natural, social and economic) in order to intergenerational equity. Sustainable development can be achieved when overlap creates between the layers of ecological, economic and social (Pourtaheri et al, 2009: 1).

The purpose of sustainability determining the minimum social requirements for long-term development (sometimes called critical social capital) and identify performance challenges of society in long-term executive jobs (Biar, 2006: 6). The emergence of the concept of sustainability in 1970 can be result of logical development and a new awareness of global environmental issues and development which in turn is influenced by factors such as the environmental movement of 60 decade and the publication of books such as growth restriction (1972) written by Danla Meadows, Silent Spring (1962) written by Rachel Carson and Closed circle (1972) written by Barry Kamono. In 1974, World Council of Churches conference was called for the realization

of a sustainable society and at that year (1974) the declaration that was adopted in the ecological development which eventually named Sustainable Development (Badri, 1997: 44-45).

The sustainable development is driving force of balanced, development, coordinated and appropriate of economic, social and cultural of all countries especially developing countries (Salami, 1997: 44). The level of urban sustainability can show quality of life in cities. Experience shows that urban sustainability has gained a lot of attention at the global level, while this issue is not taken into consideration completely in Iran. Identification and investigation the local status and bottlenecks in their development in terms of sustainability and sustainable development in cities of the issues that have been raised recently in the urban planning culture but in our country, its position has not been considered as well (Saraee et al, 2010: 37). Destruction of social unit's places in big cities without the establishment of sustainable and alternative forms is only an example of the negative effects of the development process in large cities. Neighborhood units are symbols and signs of effort and experience of the ancestors of society in cities. Whereby, via maintaining neighborhood links, they have been able to respond too many of their needs without the involvement of official institutions and government (Yahghob, 2007: 3). So following to change the conditions and factors affecting urban development in recent times man-made residential neighborhoods have had a special position in the formation of cities. Although sustainable urban development allocated a major portion of urban development literature of recent years but research in this area is still needed. Neighborhood is one of the old neighborhoods of Sardasht that somewhat managed to retain their local identity and has relatively a little potential to become a sustainable neighborhood but for complete conversion to a stable neighborhood still there are shortage and problems in various fields which according to the variety and mixing applications in this neighborhood we can by strengthening sustainability indicators converts it to a stable neighborhood.

Thus, considering the foregoing will be tried in this research is to answer the following questions:

1. Is Shabake 2 neighborhood considered a stable neighborhood in terms of economic?
2. Is Shabake 2 neighborhood considered a stable neighborhood in terms of social?
3. Is Shabake 2 neighborhood considered a stable neighborhood in terms of environment?

2. Theoretical Foundations

Neighborhood means "alley, quarter or a part from several parts of the city" (Dehkhoda, 1957). neighborhood has not had fixed and static concept in geographical and other science topics of urban knowing including urban planning, social science and political science in the past decade. At present, this concept has undergone major changes in such a way that there are many discussions about the concept and its dimensions. In fact, in each of the academic areas it has defined in its specific angle (Williams, 1985: 30). The neighborhood considered as oldest and most well-known part of towns which provides semi-public life of residents. Neighborhood usually is the body of employment and residence of 700 to 1250 households with range of 300 to 375 m (4 to 5 minute walk) that is defined by cultural element Mosque and Education (Elementary). Each neighborhood separated by a mounted network on remote neighborhood from other nearby neighborhoods (Ziari et al, 2009: 61).

From the perspective of urban planning, the neighborhood can be defined as part of the urban area or a range of applications combines supply needs of the residents in the city. In relation to the sustainable of the neighborhood, very relevant principles and criteria have been analyzed. Among these principles and criteria, we can refer to the identity and vitality, dynamism and adaptability, diversity, access, density and capacity of neighborhood (Azizi, 2006: 38). In today's society where human life is tied up with the car which in some cases is alien with human comments we require neighborhoods that as a mediate link between the city and the citizens has effective role in achieving the fundamental goals of urban planning, which is the health, comfort and beauty, and guide the city towards a pious human environment (Hanifi, 2006: 7).

Nowadays in worldwide level, there are many criticisms of modernist planning who believed in the separation of work from home and car precedence over man walking that of the most important critical views we can mention urbanism movement. The importance of dynamic life based on intimate relationships, pedestrian access to public services. Preserving valuable agricultural grounds and benefits of social capital such as facilitate collective action have brought the attention and restoring neighborhood social life especially in major cities. Revitalizing neighborhoods is the best solution to reduce time wasted in traffic neighborhood can prevent urban dispersion housing demand by providing appropriate types of housing that are created by affords of residents with the accumulation needs of residential, recreational and educational career (Kavsari Najati, Hosseini, Imani Jajarmi, Keli, 2007: 34).

In the west world studying the neighborhood as a social unit started initially by Robert Park and Rodrika Makenzi of the pioneers urban ecology of Chicago in 1926

(Shokoe, 1993: 46). The following are some of the research that has been done in relation to communities, will be discussed:

Mosavi and Bagheri Kashkoli (2012) in evaluating the spatial distribution of the quality of life in the city of Sardasht have concluded that to improve the quality of life in neighborhoods of the city of Sardasht planning in economic, physical indicators, is very impressive.

Rahnama et al (2013) in an article entitled of "*Improvement of quality of urban neighborhoods by using New Urbanism approach*" (case study: free zone of Mashhad city) concluded that existing deficiencies in the intellectual foundation of this area including purely physical perspective, has led to formation of low-quality urban structure.

Ziari (2011) investigated security and welfare in the neighborhoods of Yazd city. Results of studying hypothesis suggest that can be divided in 3 levels of security and welfare that is suitable, semi-suitable and low degree of security.

Tavassoli (2004) in his research on ancient neighborhoods of Iran, in addition to providing persistent feature of urban life in these neighborhoods have mapped old maps of these neighborhoods via existence historical and structural indicators.

Abdullahi and Mohammad Mehdi (2008) in a paper entitled with explain the sustainability criteria and indicators in the residential neighborhood by analytical review method attempts to comparative collection the views expressed in the country and the world on sustainable neighborhood. Finally, he by focusing on economic, social-cultural and environmental as basic sustainable components at global to urban scale deals with presenting the criteria and indicators for each of the basic components of sustainability in the residential neighborhood scale.

Saraee et al (2010) has done a study entitled with "*Evaluation and assessment of the sustainability of the development of the city of Babolsar*" using quantitative models and statistical software's. Results obtained from studying stable levels of development in the city of Babolsar in terms of combined indicators shows that stability coefficient is different between neighborhoods such that among 16 neighborhoods a neighborhood located in ideal stable group, two groups are in powerful sustainable group, 7 semi-sustainable neighborhoods, 4 weak sustainable neighborhoods and two neighborhoods are unsustainable.

Saraee et al (2013) conducted a research entitled with assessment social sustainability neighborhoods of Jahrom using inventory tool with 320 people and descriptive and analytical method. Results of research, Pearson correlation coefficient confirms testing hypothesis according to existing meaningful and direct relationship between variables of location belonging social trust, responsibility, sense of security,

social interaction, social participation and social sustainability at the neighborhoods of Jahrom city.

3. The study area

According to figure 1, Sardasht city has a position of 45 degrees and 28 minutes of east longitude and 36 degrees and 9 minutes and 15 seconds north latitude. This city has an area of over 1411 kilometers located in south-west of Western Azerbaijan. The height of Sardasht city from sea level is 1789 meters. According to the 2016 census, the city has 118,849 inhabitants. Of this number, 57.35% are living in the city and 42.46% live in rural areas and towns. Sardasht city divided into two sections involving Central which includes 4 rural districts (Gavrke, Baske Kolasa, Baryaji and Alan) and Vazineh district including two rural districts (Gavrke Nalin and Malkari).the characteristics of sample neighborhoods come in Table 1 (Ahmadi and Tavakkoli, 2016: 158).

Table 1: General specifications of investigated neighborhoods and the number of questionnaires distributed in Sardasht

Neighborhoods	Population 2011	Household numbers 2011	The sample population and questionnaire
Ashan	4930	1233	-
Terminal	8067	1992	-
Janbazan	2902	726	-
Doltanchk	2879	718	-
Se Rahe Maraghan	2369	592	-
Sarchave	2158	786	-
Shabake 2	N=2085	521	n = 320
Farhangian	4750	1168	-
Kanimari	1094	273	-
Grdahsor	2635	695	-
Nezaro	7298	1823	-
Sardasht	42167	10491	-
Sardasht City	118849	26546	-

Source: Municipalities Sardasht and Research Results

Figure 1: Schematic Map

4. Materials and Methods

Method research is development-applied and it's doing method is inventory. After determining the population, according to the research topic in addition to viewing the interview conversation, the required information designed according to items and research hypothesis in the form of researches questions. The population of this research is 2085 person in residents of Shabake 2 neighborhood which among them 320 person selected and as sample and has investigated. The validity of the inventory confirmed by the experts and for reliability of the inventory 320 questionnaires completed by residents of and reliability coefficient by Cranach's alpha (%81) that is acceptable statistically and it is appropriate for the reliability of the study. Ultimately, to be certain in reliability and validity of questionnaires the considered sample was completed. Finally, the collected data collected were analyzed using SPSS for/win. Ver 16 software. Data analysis in order to test hypotheses, descriptive and inferential statistics was used to prove or disprove it.

5. Research Findings

In this section, underlying variables (Age, sex, education, occupation, length of residence in the neighborhood) generally studied and then the descriptive statistics related to the sustainability criteria in the city of Sardasht and stability aspects are provided.

Table 2: Distribution of participants according to sex, age and education

Gender	Based on gender		Age groups	Based on Age groups		Education	Based on education	
	Frequency	Percent		Frequency	Percent		Frequency	Percent
Man	212	66.25	15- 19 years	36	11.25	Illiterate	2	0.63
Female	108	33.75	20- 24 years	76	23.75	Primary	8	2.5
Total	320	100%	25- 29 years	60	18.75	High School	39	12.19
			30-34 years	53	16.56	Diploma	115	35.94
			35- 39 years	16	5	BS	118	36.87
			40- 44 years	17	5.31	MA	38	11.87
			45- 49 years	2	0.63	-	-	-
			More than 50 years	15	4.69	-	-	-
			The total respondents	41	12.81	The total Respondents	320	100
			No answer	4	1.25	No answer		
			Total	320	100%	Total	320	100%

According to table 2, among the respondents according to gender, they were 212 (66.25%) males and 108 (33.75%) females.

According to table 2 the 36 (11.25%) percentage of respondents were in the category 15-19 years age, 76 persons (23.75%) percent were 20-24 age category, 60 persons (18.75%) percent in 25-29, 53 persons (16.56%) percent in 30-34, 16 persons (5%) percent in 35-39, 17 persons (5.31%) percent in 40-44, 2 persons (0.63%) percent in 45-49, and 15 (4.69%) percent are in over 50 years old. Meanwhile the lowest age group related to age group less than 45-49 years and the highest age group related to age group of 20-24.

The academic status of respondents is shown in Table 2. The highest numbers of respondents in neighborhood, according to Table 2, the number of illiterate people, 2 (0.63 percent), primary 8 (2.5 percent), high school, 39 (12.19), Diploma 115 (35.94), BA 118 (36.87) and MA 38 (11.87 percent) have been.

Table 3: Distribution of participants according to occupational groups and period of residence

Occupational groups	Occupational groups		The period of residence in the neighborhood	The period of residence in the neighborhood	
	Frequency	Percent		Frequency	Percent
Unemployed	63	19.69	Less than 5 years	67	20.94
Retired	11	3.44	5-10 years	55	17.19
Employee	39	12.19	10 - 15 years	71	22.19
Self employed	76	23.75	15 -20 years	51	15.93
Worker	81	25.31	20 -25 years	40	12.5
Other cases	32	10	25-30 years	27	8.44
No answer	18	5.62	More than 30 years	9	2.81
Total	320	100%	Total	320	100%

As can be seen in Table 3, the unemployed, the frequency of 63 (19.69 percent), 11 (3.44%) retired, 39 (12:19) employees, 76 (23.75) with the Self-employed, 81 (25.31) workers, other 32 patients (10%) and 18 (5.62) did not answered.

The research findings according to Table 3 indicate that most people stay in the neighborhood of the study from 10 to 15 years. That is show high duration of stay at that neighborhood. About 20.94 percent of people had stayed lower than 5 years, 17.19 percent 5-10 years, 15.93 percent 15-20 years, 12.5 percent 20-25 years, 8.44 percent 25-30 years, and 2.81 percent more than 30 years.

5.1 Reviews the value of sustainability in the Shabake 2 neighborhood

In order to obtain the status sustainability of neighborhood of Sardasht, one-sample t-test was used. The total Sustainable average of the neighborhood of Shabake 2 of Sardasht was 83.3. On the other hand, in the questionnaire five-item Likert scale was used and rating of 1 to 5 was assigned to answers. And the number 3 obtained as the theoretical middle of answers and average rating stability obtained was compared with the number 3. Whatever the calculated value for sustainability is smaller than 3, shows lack of sustainability and whatever this value be more the status is more sustainable.

Figure 2: Percentage of the value of respondents to the indexes of satisfaction, participation, public transport, and street furniture

Figure 2 show the response rate based on percent. According to this Figure the highest satisfaction rate of residents of Shabake 2 neighborhood 42 percent at moderate level, 18 percent at the low and high, 12 percent at the very much level, and 10 percent at the very low level have expressed their satisfaction with the neighborhood. Most of the local population participation rate is less than average which their participation rate has been low and very low. The value of dissatisfaction of residents from public transport is very high so that nearly half evaluated it as very low. This implies a lack of stability in terms of equipment and services of public transport in the neighborhood. The urban furniture in this neighborhood does not show satisfactory condition. So that 74 percent of respondent's evaluated very little the facilities of urban furniture in this neighborhood.

Figure 3: The percentage of the value of respondents to the indexes of participation rate in improvement lighting, cleanliness and walking

Figure 3 shows the percentage of the value of respondents to the indexes of participation rate in improvement lighting, cleanliness and walking. According to this Figure the participation rate of the neighborhood in improvement of the neighborhood is close to (46 percent) that this indicates the importance of modernization and improvement of the neighborhood for residents, lighting passages 50% on average, is the highest value, the cleanliness of neighborhood 48% in mediate level, and the important value of biking and walking has less important and 40 percent answered very low.

Figure 4: The percentage of the value of respondents to the indexes of Noise pollution, notification, public, and leisure complexes for children

Figure 4 shows the percentage of the value of respondents to the indexes of Noise pollution, notification, public and leisure complexes for children. According to this chart, noise pollution of the environment have evaluated the most respondents at the average and low level. 90 percent of respondents noticed the leisure time of children at very low level that indicated non sustainability of this index in the neighborhood. Public complexes have noticed 62 percent of them as very low and 66 percent have noticed the value of notification as very low that this indicates unsustainability at these kinds of indexes.

Figure 5: The percentage of the value of respondents to the indexes of quality of streets, access to services and acting Mayor

The percentage of value respondents to the qualities of quality of streets, access to services and acting mayor to improve the neighborhood of not have favorable condition. According to figure 5 the quality of passages of the neighborhood, 72

percentages of respondents stated at very weak level.44 percent evaluated access value to the services at average level and 60 percent stated the actions of mayor at very weak level and 22 percent stated as weak.

Table 4: Average stability of each of studied indices in neighborhood of Sardasht

Indicators	Sustainability Average	STDEV	Variance	Sustainability status
To what extent your neighborhood is attractive for you?	2.96	1.12	1.26	Unstable
How is the participation rate of neighborhood residents to improve the current situation?	3.98	0.82	0.67	Stable
To what extent public transportation (taxi, etc.) meets your population neighborhood?	4.17	1.00	0.99	Stable
To what extent the urban furniture (benches, boxes, telephone boxes, etc.) is available?	4.67	0.69	0.48	Stable
To what extent privacy lighting in your neighborhood, especially at night, is provided?	1.69	0.83	0.69	Unstable
To what extent you would like to contribute to the improvement of your neighborhood?	3.14	0.89	0.79	Stable
How is the cleanliness neighborhood (garbage collection, sewage disposal, etc.) in your neighborhood?	3.24	1.07	1.15	Stable
To what extent biking and walking is important in your neighborhood?	3.74	1.23	1.50	Stable
Is the noise from cars, disrupted the peace of residents	3.26	1.08	1.18	Stable
Is there space for children to play in your neighborhood?	4.88	0.39	0.15	Stable
Are there spaces for gathering and social interaction of residents in the neighborhood?	4.52	0.71	0.50	Stable
Is there spaces to inform and raise the awareness of residents in the neighborhood?	4.58	0.67	0.45	Stable
How is quality of streets in your neighborhood (the asphalt and sidewalks)?	4.66	0.63	0.39	Stable
How is your access to municipal services (shopping, schools, parks, etc.)?	3.50	0.93	0.87	Stable
How do you evaluate the measures of municipal to improve the performance of neighborhood?	4.40	0.83	0.69	Stable
	3.83			

According to table 4 that represents sustainability and unsustainability according to the comments of respondents, it shows that about economic indexes there is an unsustainable neighborhood. Average sustainability in each of these indices respectively equals to 2.96 and 1.69. The stability of public transport, the urban furniture, the Acting and performance of mayor, spaces for gathering and social interaction of residents in the neighborhood, play areas for children and neighborhood

quality of streets are at medium level and the mean of these indexes is more than 4 which indicates sustainability of these indexes in Shabake 2 neighborhood. Participation rate, the Privacy of Street lighting in neighborhoods, neighborhood cleanliness, the importance of biking and walking, noise pollution and the access to municipal services with sustainability rate of more than 3 in the view of respondents. Thus, the total average of Sardasht equals to 3.83. Whatever the calculated value to sustainability is smaller than 3 is indicative of the lack of sustainability and whatever the amount is more, the situation is more stable. According to this table, most respondents have evaluated an average sustainability at acceptable levels. Given that, the average rating of neighborhood is almost 3.83. Based on a stable level of mentioned neighborhood in the view of the respondents has evaluated at moderate and good level.

Figure 6: The current situation of sustainable level of Shabake 2 neighborhood according to Likert spectrum

Table 5: The analysis of the correlation rate between the variables of urban sustainability and respondents in the neighborhood

Indicators	Variables	Permissible error	Significance level	Correlation Coefficient (R)
Social	Satisfaction rate	0.05	0.009	0.541*
	Participation rate	0.05	0.029	0.236**
	Urban furniture rate	0.05	0.016	0.329*
	Notification rate	0.05	0.028	0.576*
Economic	Neighborhood Improvement	0.05	0.012	0.417
	Privacy of passage lighting	0.05	0.019	0.612
	Facilities and equipment	0.05	0.015	0.425
	The availability of municipal services (buy)	0.05	0.009	0.503
	Public transport services	0.05	0.016	0.638*
	Performance and municipal actions to improve neighborhood	0.05	0.036	0.401*
Environment	Cleaning neighborhood	0.05	0.025	0.251
	Noise Pollution	0.05	0.011	0.396
	Passages quality neighborhood (the asphalt)	0.05	0.008	0.521

Based on the correlations findings of this study in Table 5, the attitude rate of more than half of the respondents, despite the small number of sustainability service centers at neighborhood, had relatively positive, than sustainability of the neighborhood.

The obtained results from discussed investigations about participation and satisfaction had positive and meaningful relationship rate with correlation coefficient and 0.541 and 0.236 at level of 0.05 and 0.01. Intensity of the relationship in this type of activity is powerful in terms of ranking and shows sustainability in this index.

Results obtained from discussed studies neighborhood improvements, public lighting space, facilities and equipment, access to municipal services (purchase), there is positive relationship with correlation coefficient 0.417, 0.425 and 0.503 at 0.05 levels. But the relationship is not significant and does not comply with the opinion of the respondents in the neighborhood. But in the public transport service indicators and performance and measures of municipality to improve the neighborhood, there is positive and meaningful relationship with correlation coefficient 0.638 and 0.431 at 0.05 levels. Between environmental indicators and each of its components, no relationship was observed. The calculated correlation coefficient for environmental indicators (neighborhood cleanliness, Noise Pollution and the quality of neighborhood passages) with correlation coefficient of 0.251 and 0.521 at 0.05 level that there is no meaningful relationship.

According to conducted analysis based on one sample T-test for each of the indicators the most desirable steady state for the town of Sardasht is in social index and the most unfavorable mode is related to economic and environmental parameters. Examine aspects and dimensions of sustainability at the levels of Sardasht neighborhood shows that that this neighborhood has many differences in terms of having these indices. Based on the spatial distribution of stable levels neighborhood was realized in two major category that are distinguishable, which the first category including locations with acceptable stable levels more in West and North West and mainly based on the city's affluent areas and the second category includes weak and sustainable areas which are in east and northeast and comply with the slums of the city of which there is a significant difference between the two municipal level. The current trend is a major challenge in achieving sustainable urban development. Hence, according to the importance of sustainability category, it is necessary to achieve favorable and fix heterogeneity, the neighborhood that located in low level must be at the first priority and by using modern and efficient solutions to reduce different effects and unsustainability aspects and dualism space do new steps. The way to reach sustainability passes through neighborhood development and this is not achieved without considering institutional, human, cultural, economic, and individual and collective capacities. According to the table of index averages can be concluded that the average value of each of the sub-indices (socio-economic-environmental) in the inventory is acceptable to the value of upper and lower limit and this is certain that

each index that goes toward improvement makes the neighborhood better and enhances the sustainable development and generally it can be said that by enhancing local sustainable development, the urban places will achieve to sustainable development.

6. Conclusion

Change and transformation is inevitable in urban environments and various factors including social, demographic, economic, technological and environmental factors are effective in the process and the weak and intensity of these changes. The changes in the population structure with immigration or attracting migrates of neighborhoods with a decisive impact on housing conditions influences the body of the neighborhoods. In the form of economic forces, change in the price of land and housing and fluctuations in constructions is effective on bearable capacity of the neighborhood. Technology forces are effective in different aspects influencing the quality and quantity of buildings and transport networks. In a cultural force, it can be said that despite the similarity of the human body needs. Tendencies and cultural values could be very different that appeared in the local space environment. Following, changes in the condition and effective factors on expansion and urban development in the recent times. Man-made residential neighborhoods have special status in the formation of cities. While sustainable urban development is allocated the bulk of the urban literature in recent years, addressing the principles and criteria for sustainable neighborhood development still requires a lot of research. Sardasht neighborhood still is an unsustainable neighborhood that is result of unplanned planning. The findings indicate that the principles and sustainability criteria such as neighborhood identity, vitality, access, diversity, providing services and security, in lower level has been achieved in the neighborhood. However, what is considered as alarm and serious concern is bearable capacity of neighborhood. Neighborhood has achieved to the threshold of demographic and construction capacities and in the case that continuous monitoring as a matter of principle be neglected principles and standards that so far have ensured an unstable neighborhood, will be more. Thus, in addition to the usual principles in planning and design of the environment, the main principle of carrying capacity must be observed in serious consideration as a decisive and inevitable to stability of neighborhood. An assessment model is using views on residents about the stability of their neighborhoods. The results showed that the stability of the neighborhood in the views of residents have been at medium level. In order to determine the level of stability in this neighborhood one-sample T-test was used and it became clear that the current

sustainability status of Shabake2 neighborhood from the perspective of a healthy city is 3.83. In other words, these indicators are most effective in the sustainability of the neighborhood. And among these factors, the security rate of the neighborhood is highest and most effective among other factors. Neighborhood residents are relatively satisfy from key and environment f indicators, they are unsatisfied from economic indicators and are satisfied from social indicators.

Despite the importance of the issue of determining the real extent of the neighborhoods, So far in many urban development plans less attention has been paid to this matter. At the neighborhood level, should be established extensive links between residents. Face-to-face encounters, provides residents the use of public spaces, interaction and desirable mental space. This is the result of internal homogeneity that leads to the space identity. The identity of space, followed by enhances the sense of belonging and continuity of social life – physical. In such situations, sense of cooperation and collaboration among individual's increases and desirable life environment will be its gift. Attachment to the neighborhood, intensified social control and popular participation (as the success of any scheme) increases while various factors have reduced the possibility of this feature as a property neighborhood. The most important of these factors can be found in the entry and spread of private cars in the lives of citizens. In modern contexts, what is that have no position is "social relations". It is natural that in such circumstances the favor neighbor yesterday, today considered annoying neighbor. And good neighbors are those who not interfering each other

References

1. Abdollahi, Majid, Mozaffar Sarrafi and Jmileh Tavakkoli Nia (2010), Theoretical study with emphasis and redefine the concept of neighborhood.
2. Ahmadi, Shirko and Tavakkoli, Morteza, 2016, Assessment and evaluation the sustainability status of the neighborhoods of Sardasht, Journal of geography and spatial planning urban - regional, Volume 6, Issue 20, pp. 153- 170.
3. Atlas of Astronomy,2006, Geographic and Cartographic Institute of mapping agency of Iran, Department of Planning and Budget
4. Azizi, M. M. (2006), Stable residential neighborhood: a case study NARMAK, fine arts magazine, No. 27, Tehran University.
5. Azizi, Mohammad Mehdi; (2006) "Stable residential area, Narmak Case Study," Journal of Fine Arts; 27.

6. Badri, Ali (1997), Sustainable Development: Concept and valuable and practical, Geographical Research Quarterly, Issue 48.
7. Biart, M. (2002) 'Social sustainability as part of the social agenda of the European community', in Ritt.T. (Ed.): Soziale Nachhaltigkeit: Von der Umweltpolitik zur Nachhaltigkeit?
8. Civil Registration Department of Sardasht.2006 city of Sardasht.
9. Dehkhoda, A. A. (1957), Dictionary, Volume 9, Tehran: Cirrus publication,
10. Hekmat Naba, Hassan and Ali Zangi Abadi (2004), an analysis of stable levels in the city of Yazd and strategies to improve it, Geographical Research Quarterly, No. 72 pp 51-37.
11. Hossein Zadeh, Reza and others (2011), assessment of environmental sustainability in urban areas using technology decisions.
12. Mousavi, Mir Najaf and Ali Bagheri Kashkouli (2012), evaluating the spatial distribution of the quality of life in the city of Sardasht, Research and Urban Planning, Issue IX, pp. 116- 95.
13. Mousavi, Mir Najaf and Ali Bagheri Kashkouli (2012), evaluating the spatial distribution of the quality of life in the city of Sardasht, Research and Urban Planning, Issue IX, pp. 116- 95.
14. Rahnama, Mohammad Rahim and Mohammed Mohsen Razavi (2012), the study impact of Makani Hosseinhalgh on social capital and participation in the neighborhoods of Mashhad city Fine Arts Journal, Volume 17, Number 2, Ss.36-29.
15. Salami, R. (1997) Overview sustainable development approach Magazine, Number 17, Tehran,
16. Saraee, Mohammed Hussein, Lotfi, S. and Ibrahim, S. (2010) Evaluating and monitoring sustainable development in Babolsar city neighborhoods, and urban planning study, first year, second edition, pp. 60-37.
17. Saraee, Mohammed Hussein, Rosta, M., Mir Jalili, and Ehsan Asadi, Amir (2013) evaluate the social sustainability of the neighborhoods of Jahrom city. Geography and urban planning Zagros, Volume 5, Number 15146-131.
18. Shakuie, H. (1993), urban social geography, social ecology of the city, The SID (Majed), Second Edition.
19. Soltani, Laila Ali Mahin Zangiabadi, and N. (2011), Urban planning in order to promote Iranian-Islamic identity by emphasizing the role of women in urban neighborhoods, Journal of Iranian-Islamic city, the fourth number, pp 36-29.
20. Tavassoly, Mahmoud (2004) .constructing and Architecture of city in hot and dry climates Pyam publication 1948.

21. Williams, Michael, (1985), *Neighborhood Organizations: Seeds of a New Urban Life*, We Sport, Greenwood Press.
22. Zakerian, Maliha, Mir Najaf Mousavi and Ali Bagheri Kashkouli Najaf (2010), *Analysis of the Population Distribution and Distribution Service gets from the perspective of sustainable development in urban areas*, *Journal of Research and Urban Planning*, the first, second, pp 84-61
23. Ziari K. A. (2005), *Planning new cities*, Tehran, SAMT, PP 79-80.
24. Ziari K. A. (2005), *Urban land use planning*, Yazd University Press, second edition.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Social Sciences Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).